

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Chromium(III) containing some Bidentate Amines and Quadridentate Schiff Base Ligands

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A number of new mixed ligand complexes of chromium(III) using two diamines and three Schiff bases have been synthesised, having the compositions : $[\text{CrL}_2\text{X}_2]\text{X}\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2^2-)(\text{NCS})_2]\text{NCS}$, $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^2-)(\text{NCS})_2]\text{NCS}$, $[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2)(\text{NCS})_2]\text{NCS}$, where $\text{L} = \text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_2$ or $\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{NH}_2$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or NCS ; $n = 0$ or 4 . Molar conductance data reveal that dichloro and thiocyanato complexes of the diamines, thiocyanato complexes of the salicylaldehyde Schiff base of triethylene tetramine and thiophene 2-aldehyde Schiff base of *N,N*-bisdiaminoethyl-1,3-propanediamine are 1 : 1 electrolytes in DMSO while thiocyanato complex with 1,6-diaminohexane is 1 : 1 electrolyte in nitromethane. But dichloro complex with 1,3-diaminopropane and thiocyanato complex of salicylaldehyde Schiff base of 1,3-diaminopropane are non-electrolytes. Magnetic and spectral data support octahedral stereochemistry for the complexes.

Recently there has been considerable interest in the synthetic¹⁻⁴ and kinetic^{2,5} aspects of chromium(III) complexes of macrocyclic ligands. This is because that macrocyclic ligands occur in the structures of a number of the most prominent biologically important natural complexes, such as 16-membered inner ring in the porphyrin ligand of the heme proteins and a 15-membered inner ring in the corrin ligand of vitamin B₁₂. A number of interesting reports on Cr^{III}, Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} complexes containing [14]_{ane}N₄, [15]_{ane}N₄, [16]_{ane}N₄, [18]_{ane}N₄, [14]_{ane}N₆ and their derivatives have appeared quite recently⁶⁻⁸. There seems to have been no report on complexation of Cr^{III} containing (i) thiocyanato and quadridentate Schiff base moiety, (ii) thiocyanato and diamine moiety and (iii) chloro and long-chain diamino moieties. Kinetic studies are yet to be carried out. The present investigation describes synthesis and characterisation of the above types of complexes. Kinetic studies of some of the complexes will be the subject of a number of forthcoming reports.

Results and Discussion

The mixed ligand complexes (Table 1) have been

formulated on the basis of elemental analyses and conductance, magnetic, ir and electronic spectral data. Complexes 2, 3, 5 and 7 are soluble in DMSO and show conductance value in the range 24–31 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ consistent with 1:1 electrolyte⁹. Complex 6 is also soluble in DMSO but shows molar conductance of 8 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ consistent with nonelectrolytic nature of the complex⁹. Complexes 1 and 4 are soluble in nitromethane and show conductance value of 0.0 and 88 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹ respectively, consistent with a nonelectrolytic and 1 : 1 electrolytic values of the complexes⁹.

Ir spectral data of complexes 1–4 display ν_{NH₂} modes (symmetric and asymmetric)^{3,6,10} in the region 2 860–3 220 cm⁻¹ whereas those of the original diamine ligands at 3 295–3 360 cm⁻¹. This shift towards the lower frequency suggests that the amino nitrogens are coordinated to Cr^{III} ion in these cases. This is further supported by the appearance of ν_{Cr-N} mode^{7,10,11} at 510–530 cm⁻¹ in the far-ir spectra of the complexes. The thiocyanato complexes 3–7 display ν_{CN} stretching modes at 2 065–2 090 cm⁻¹ characteristic of N-bonded thiocyanato moiety thereby supporting that the metal ion behaves as

a hard acid centre^{11,12}. The Cr–NCS bonding is further supported by the appearance of ν_{CS} modes at higher frequencies (1 025–1 060 cm^{-1}) in the complexes. The metal-nitrogen linkage of these complexes is further supported by the appearance of ν_{Cr-N} modes at 530–590 cm^{-1} in the far-ir spectra of the complexes. Complexes 5 and 6 exhibit $\nu_{C=N}$ band at 1 600–1 610 cm^{-1} , indicating coordination of the nitrile nitrogen of the Schiff base moiety. The disappearance of ν_{OH} band (3 400 cm^{-1}) in these complexes indicates deprotonation and coordination at the oxygen site. This is further supported by ν_{C-O} mode at 1 150 and ν_{Cr-O} mode at 440–450 cm^{-1} in the far-ir region of spectra of the complexes. The coordination at sulphur of the Schiff base moiety in complex 7 is indicated by the appearance of ν_{Cr-S} band at 400 cm^{-1} in the far-ir region of the spectrum. Complexes 1, 3 and 4 exhibit ν_{OH} bands at 3 400–3 420 cm^{-1} characteristic of lattice water molecules.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND COLOUR OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd no	Complex/ (Colour)	Analysis % Found / (Calcd)		
		C	H	N
1	[Cr(NH ₂ (CH ₂) ₃ NH ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl 4H ₂ O (Bluish violet)	19.1 (19.0)	5.3 (5.3)	14.7 (14.8)
2	[Cr(NH ₂ (CH ₂) ₆ NH ₂) ₂ Cl ₂]Cl (Blue)	36.8 (36.9)	8.1 (8.2)	14.1 (14.3)
3	[Cr(NH ₂ (CH ₂) ₃ NH ₂) ₂ (NCS) ₂]NCS 4H ₂ O (Bluish violet)	24.1 (24.2)	4.5 (4.5)	21.9 (22.0)
4	[Cr(NH ₂ (CH ₂) ₆ NH ₂) ₂ (NCS) ₂](NCS) 4H ₂ O (Blue)	34.1 (34.0)	6.0 (6.0)	18.5 (18.5)
5	[Cr(C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₂ ²⁻)(NCS) ₂]NCS (Greenish yellow)	41.4 (41.5)	4.1 (4.2)	16.8 (16.9)
6	[Cr(C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ ²⁻)(NCS) ₂]NCS (Olive)	40.3 (40.3)	3.1 (3.2)	13.6 (13.8)
7	[Cr(C ₁₇ H ₂₄ N ₄ S ₂)(NCS) ₂]NCS (Pink)	35.4 (35.5)	4.3 (4.2)	17.0 (17.1)

The magnetic measurements on complexes 1–7 at 25° reveal that all the complexes are paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.51\text{--}4.22$ B.M.) corresponding to three unpaired electrons. Magnetic measurements thus support O_h symmetry of the complexes⁶.

Structural information is further supported from the $d-d$ spectral bands in the complexes. Complexes 1, 2 and 6 exhibit three spin-allowed transitions ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (610–692), ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) (525–549) and ${}^4A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P) (385–410 nm), while the cor-

responding transitions for the complexes 3–5 and 7 obtained at 528–557, 394–404 and 270–330 nm respectively, are being consistent with octahedral stereochemistry of the chromium(III) complexes¹³. The fourth band of the complexes 1, 5, 6 and 7 around 270–311 nm is probably caused by charge transfer.

Experimental

All chemicals (E. Merck) were of reagent grade and used as such except for ethanol which was purified by refluxing the 99% crude with iodine and magnesium turnings and finally distilled.

Salicylaldehyde Schiff base of 1,3-diaminopropane (C₁₇H₁₆N₂O₂H₂): To an ethanolic solution of 1,3-diaminopropane (0.01 mol, 30 ml), a solution of salicylaldehyde (0.02 mol) in the same solvent (40 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2.5 h. It was then left overnight in a refrigerator and the resulting yellow solid was washed with cold ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaO, m.p. 52.3° (Found: C, 72.2, H, 6.4, N, 9.8. Calcd. for . C, 72.3; H, 6.4; N, 9.9%)

Salicylaldehyde Schiff base of triethylenetetramine (tet) (C₂₀H₂₄N₄O₂H₂): An ethanolic solution of triethylenetetramine (tet) (0.02 mol, 25 ml) was added to a solution of salicylaldehyde (0.04 mol) in the same solvent (50 ml). Yellow product that appeared immediately was washed with ether and dried under reduced pressure over P₄O₁₀ (Found: C, 67.7; H, 7.3; N, 15.7. Calcd. for . C, 67.87; H, 7.3; N, 15.8%).

Thiophene-2-aldehyde Schiff base of N,N-bis-diaminoethyl-1,3-propanediamine (C₁₇H₂₄N₄S₂): An ethanolic solution of N,N-bis(diaminoethyl)-1,3-propanediamine (2,3,2-tet; 0.01 mol, 25 ml) was added to a solution of thiophene-2-aldehyde (0.02 mol) in the same solvent (25 ml) and then heated at ~ 75° for 0.5 h when its volume was reduced to ca. 25 ml. It was then left for a few days for evaporation in air and the resulting brown gummy product was stored under reduced pressure over fused CaCl₂.

[CrL₂Cl₂]Cl.nH₂O [L' = NH₂CH₂CH₂CH₂NH₂ or NH₂(CH₂)₆NH₂] (1 and 2). *General method*: An ethanolic solution of the diamine ligand (0.02 mol,

25 ml) was added to a solution of $\text{CrCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol) in the same solvent (50 ml) and heated at 45° with stirring for 5–10 min. The resulting bluish violet solid was washed with cold ethanol and dried under reduced pressure over fused CaCl_2 .

$[\text{CrL}''_2(\text{NCS})_2]\text{NCS} \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ [$\text{L}'' = \text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{NH}_2$ or $\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_6\text{NH}_2$] (3 and 4). *General method* : An ethanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (0.03 mol, 40 ml) was added to a solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.01 mol) in the same solvent (50 ml) when a white precipitate of KNO_3 separated out which was filtered off. To the pink coloured filtrate an ethanolic solution of the diamine ligand (0.02 mol, 20 ml) was added with stirring. The resulting bluish solid was washed with ethanol and stored as above.

$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2^-)](\text{NCS})_2$ (5) : To an ethanolic solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.001 mol, 30 ml), a solution of potassium thiocyanate (0.003 mol) in the same solvent (30 ml) was added when a white precipitate of KNO_3 separated out which was filtered off. To the pink coloured filtrate an ethanolic solution of the Schiff base ligand, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{H}_2$ (0.001 mol, 40 ml) was added with stirring. The resulting greenish yellow solid was washed with cold ethanol and stored as above.

$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2^-)](\text{NCS})_2\text{NCS}$ (6) : An ethanolic solution of potassium thiocyanate (0.006 mol, 30 ml) was added to a solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.002 mol) in the same solvent (30 ml) when a white precipitate of KNO_3 separated out which was filtered off. To the pink coloured filtrate an ethanolic solution of the Schiff base ligand, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{H}_2$ (0.002 mol, 40 ml) was added and heated at $\sim 50^\circ$ for 20 min with stirring. The resulting greenish solid was then allowed to settle at room temperature, filtered, washed with cold ethanol and stored as above.

$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2)](\text{NCS})_2\text{NCS}$ (7) : To an ethanolic solution of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.004 mol, 30 ml), a solution of potassium thiocyanate (0.012 mol) in the same solvent (30 ml) was added when a white precipitate of KNO_3 separated out which was filtered off. To the filtrate an ethanolic solution of the Schiff base ligand, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_4\text{S}_2$ (40 ml) was added and

heated at $\sim 50^\circ$ for 0.5 h with stirring. The resulting greyish violet product was allowed to settle down overnight to yield a product of gummy nature. It was then separated and dried under reduced pressure over P_4O_{10} .

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP₃-300 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra (nujol) on a LKB Biochrom Ultrospee spectrophotometer at 25° . Conductivities of 10^{-3} – 10^{-4} M solutions of the complexes in dimethyl sulphoxide and nitromethane, were measured at 30° with a digital conductometer (Konductometer C G 857 Scotte Geratte) and a dip type cell with platinised electrodes. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was made with a Johnson-Mathey balance at 25° . Carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen analyses were carried out by the microanalytical services at Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow.

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